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LITERATURE REVIEW

Mutualism and its influence on evolution

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Introduction

Holland et al. [33] define mutualism as “an interaction between individuals of different species that results in positive (beneficial) effect on per capita reproduction and/or survival of the interacting populations”. Benefits given by one species to another can take different forms, such as services, like protection, shelter, or seed dispersal, often in exchange for resources, like food or nutrients. The best-known example is pollination, where animals (e.g., insects, birds or even bats) transfer plant pollen in exchange for nectar. Another example is ant-plant mutualism, where ants protect the host plant by repelling herbivores, while in exchange, plants provide extrafloral nectar (through *nectaries*) and shelter (through structures called *domatia*). This kind of relationship can be obligated (one species cannot survive without the other) or facultative. The term “mutualism” was used for the first time in 1878 by Beneden [5], but only a few ecologists were interested in mutualism until the 1970s. For Holland et al. [33], two reasons explain this lack of interest.

Firstly, mutualism was seen as more interesting from an evolutionary point of view rather than an ecological one. Indeed, the existence of mutualism was a challenge for Darwin, as species acting (and possibly evolving) for the benefit of others could not fit in his theory of natural selection, where species evolve to increase their reproductive fitness.

The second reason is linked to the development of theoretical ecology, which focused on competition and predation in the early twentieth century and led to the so-called Lotka-Volterra models [46, 71]. While these models predict bounded population growth, similar models that consider mutualism predict unbounded population growth and thus were considered unreliable. Boucher et al. [8] suggested that ecologists also didn't study mutualism because of “its association with left-wing politics”.

Nowadays, mutualism is widely studied, both from the ecological and the evolutionary point of view, more importantly in the context of global change, where the extinction of a few species can trigger cascading extinctions of many more [41]. Understanding the mechanisms underlying mutualistic relationships can help mitigate these threats. By extension, investigating the evolutionary aspects of mutualism can help acquire insights into how these ecological mechanisms arose and evolved. Bronstein et al. [12] categorise these studies around five questions:

1. Which conditions influence the existence and maintenance of mutualism?
2. How do mutualistic traits appear and evolve?
3. Which factors can influence the coevolution/cospeciation of mutualistic partners?
4. Which conditions influence the appearance and maintenance of different degrees of specialisation and generalisation? How does dependence evolve?
5. How do cheaters appear? Why cheating does not make mutualism a disadvantage?

Unfortunately, observational and experimental works have limits, as evolutionary processes take hundreds of thousands of years and are thus difficult to identify and quantify. Investigating these

questions theoretically through mathematical modelling can improve our understanding of mutualism and its involvement in evolution.

1 Origins and maintenance of mutualism

Fossil records of extinct plant and animal species give us an idea of when some mutualistic interactions appeared. For example, pollination by insects appeared at least 250 million years ago, as fossils indicate that some plants from the late Paleozoic had large prepollen that could not be carried by the wind, and others show the presence of prepollen in insect guts from early Permian and Mid-Mesozoic. But as interesting as it is to know when mutualism arose, an even more interesting question is which conditions can promote (or prevent) its appearance or its breakdown.

Origins of mutualism

Mutualism implies that both sides of the interaction find some benefits to interacting with each other. As explained earlier, benefits can be food, shelter, and dispersal, but how does it arise in the first place? How did two species start to cooperate? There are two ways mutualism can arise: through chance or from antagonism.

Partners by chance: As explained by Weiblen et al. [72] and Janzen [37], a mutualism between two species could start “with little or no history of association”, and thus would find its origin in the meeting between these species. An example from Janzen [37] is a frugivore colonizing the environment of a tree species, where tree fruit traits coincide with dietary and digestive traits allowing seed dispersal.

From antagonism to mutualism: A second explanation for the appearance of mutualism is the shift from an antagonistic to a mutualistic interaction. An example of this shift is brood pollination, defined as “specialized interactions in which plants are pollinated by insects and where their larvae consume seeds of the same plants” [32, 72].

A mechanism that could promote the appearance of mutualism is sensory trap, mimetic signals that can induce out-of-context behaviour such as cooperation [21].

Maintenance and breakdown

As well as a mutualistic relationship between species can arise, it can also disappear, which seems to have happened many times in different types of mutualisms. The interest in how mutualism can disappear has been motivated in the last decades by concern about climate change, as mutualism breakdown could accelerate the consequences of environmental changes on biodiversity [41, 3]. Sachs et al. [62] predict three ways mutualism can break down:

(A) Extinction of mutualistic partners: Firstly, mutualism can disappear because species involved in it go extinct. It could particularly be the case of obligate mutualism, where the extinction of one partner can lead the other to go extinct (Figure 1.A).

(B) Shift from mutualism to parasitism: A way to minimise costs is to decrease rewards given to the other partner, which could slowly lead to parasitic interaction (Figure 1.B). However, as explained by Sachs et al. [62], two factors could prevent this shift to parasitism: if it is a by-product mutualism or if it is reciprocal.

(C) Abandonment of mutualism: Mutualism can breakdown when species stop interacting with each other, which can happen in two ways:

(i) The return to autonomy, when partners stop all kinds of mutualistic interaction. This is for example the case of obligate defence mutualism between species of the Neotropical genus *Cecropia* and the ant species *Azteca* Gutiérrez-Valencia et al. [30] (Figure 1.C)

(ii) The switch to novel partners, which can happen through the invasion of a new potential partner, and can have long-term consequences on the biodiversity of the community [28, 45] (Figure 1.C).

Figure 1 – Illustration of the different ways mutualism can break down. **(A)** Partner goes extinct. **(B)** Interaction shifts from mutualism to parasitism. **(C)** Partners stop interacting with each other **(i)**, or one of them switches to a novel partner **(ii)**.

Three mechanisms can prevent mutualism breakdown: host sanction [26], where one species controls the provision of benefits according to the partner’s behaviour, and thus avoids the transition from mutualism to parasitism. Filtering, which allows individuals to prevent or limit interactions with parasitic or low-quality partners [38]. And tolerance, defined by Lars Raberg as “the ability of a host to limit the health or fitness effect of a given infection intensity” [59], can play a key role in the shift from parasitism to mutualism, as it can reduce the cost of interacting with the parasitic species.

2 Evolution of mutualistic traits

Mutualistic interactions involve a variety of traits that can be dedicated to it, for example, those that attract mutualistic partners or those which reward them. It can also involve traits that were not originally linked to mutualism. Current questions around these traits focus on when and why they arise, and how mutualism can shape them.

Origins of mutualistic traits

One way to determine if two extinct species were mutualistic partners is to observe if they have functional traits like those found in actual partners. However, one can wonder if these traits appeared before or after the beginning of mutualism. In the case of insect pollination, there are questions about the origins of floral colours and scents for the plant, and of colour vision and odour reception for insects. In other words, did colour vision evolve after, before, or at the same time as floral colours? Kooi et al. [43] explained that as colour vision is also used by insects to detect potential mates or predators, it seems highly unlikely that colour vision appearance was driven by floral colours. One explanation would be that colouration followed pollination to make the flower more visible to insects, thus improving fitness by increasing pollination frequency. A similar question concerns the origins of fleshy fruits [47].

Nonreciprocal evolution of mutualistic traits

Plant-insect mutualism involves (almost) exclusively one mobile partner (the animal) and one fixed partner (the plant), leading to quite different selection pressures for both. Indeed, in insect pollination, foraging behaviour can decrease the selective pressure that plants impose on the insect if alternative partners are available. Moreover, the fact that many mutualistic interactions are asymmetric (one species is a specialist and the other a generalist) can also decrease the selection pressure one species can apply to the generalist one. A central example of nonreciprocal evolution is the evolution of floral traits influenced by pollinators.

Indeed, in the case of zoophily (i.e. pollination by animals), plant reproduction success relies almost exclusively on pollinator visit frequencies. Thus, sexual selection, which promotes traits increasing reproduction success, selects traits increasing those visits. Fenster et al. [22] define *pollination syndromes* as “a suit of floral traits, including rewards, associated with the attraction and utilization of a specific group of animals as pollinators.” In other words, plants that interact with pollinators belonging to the same functional group should exhibit similar floral traits, such that colour, shape or scent. For example, Schiestl et al. [64] describe how pollinators have shaped floral signals to attract them by being more easily detected (e.g., the colour of the flower), but also to indicate more rewards (e.g., the size of the flower). Pollination syndromes are good examples of nonreciprocal evolution, as in this scenario, only plants’ evolutionary trajectories are influenced by interaction with pollinators. However, as we will see in the next section, the evolution of some pollination traits can

be reciprocal, and this phenomenon is called coevolution.

Another example of non-reciprocal evolution can be found in insect–fungus mutualisms, as described by Biedermann et al. [6]. From the insect point of view, mutualism can lead to the appearance of fungal spore-carrying organs, also called *mycangia*, in order to disperse the mutualistic fungi, but can also lead to the development of social behaviour to improve the outcome of the relationship, for example providing new substrate to the fungi. From the fungi perspective, mutualism can also lead to morphological changes, for example, the production of “nutrient- and enzyme-rich *conidia*”, also called *ambrosia* structure, *gongylidia* or nodules.

3 Coevolution, cospeciation & diversification

Mutualism is known to influence biodiversity. However, several studies show that determining how mutualism drives species richness is complex, as it involves different ecological and evolutionary mechanisms [17]. Thompson [65] defines *coevolution* as a “reciprocal evolutionary change among interacting species driven by natural selection”. This necessity to clearly define coevolution originally came from Janzen [37], who thought that this term was misused to describe matching traits in interacting species (e.g., fruits traits of a mammal-dispersed seed and mammal’s dietary needs), matching that in some cases are not the results of coevolution.

This parallel process where species influence each other’s evolution can lead to *cospeciation*, a “macroevolutionary pattern of speciation in which two or more interacting lineages undergo matched speciation events during their phylogenetic history” [65]. However, there exist other mechanisms through which mutualism can influence biodiversity through the increase or decrease of extinction and speciation rates.

Coevolution: a complex and subtle mechanism

As explained by Anderson [1], after Janzen’s appeal for better use of the term in the 1980s, the main studies about coevolution focused on “obligately specialised mutualisms and highly specialised parasitisms”, as coevolution was thought to be more susceptible to happen between two species interacting strongly with each other. However, in the same decade, the recognition that mutualistic interactions are, in many cases, not only between two species but between many, as well as they can also be highly asymmetrical (one partner interacting with many species while the other one has only a few) complexified its detection. Fortunately, Anderson [1] gives us three essential steps for him to efficiently identify coevolution. The first step is to determine which traits of both species are susceptible to coevolve and predict how these traits would evolve to fit together. The second step is then to show that these traits are subject to evolutionary pressure and that this selective pressure comes from the mutualistic partner. Finally, the last step is to demonstrate that these traits have evolved according to the interaction.

The Geographic Mosaic of Coevolution

Since the late 1990s, a new approach to study coevolution spread, one that considers the spatial and temporal variability of interactions. This new framework commonly called the “Geographic Mosaic of Coevolution” and defined by J.N Thompson [66, 68, 67] is organised around three main hypotheses. The first one is that the selective pressure one species applies to another depends on its environment. Indeed, abiotic and biotic conditions influence the way species are interacting, and thus affect the impact of their interactions on their evolutionary trajectories. The second hypothesis states that there exists what Thompson calls “evolutionary hot spots”, communities where coevolution occurs. In contrast, there are also “evolutionary cold spots”, where the reciprocal selection of one species on another is either weak, asymmetrical, or nonexistent. The third and last hypothesis is that there is “a continual geographic remixing of the range of coevolving traits”, which is the result of the previous mechanisms (selection mosaic and coevolutionary hot spots), but also gene flows between geographically separated populations and their possible extinction, as well as random genetic drifts.

This framework has been successfully applied to mutualism, for example, to plant-pollinator mutualism [2], and mutualistic interaction between ants and wild cotton [61].

Patterns of coevolution

As mutualism is profitable for both partners, one could expect that they should evolve to facilitate interactions, which can lead to matching mutualistic traits, such as the matching between the shape and size of the prostomata of some myrmecophytic plants and the shape and size of the ants associated with them [13], or the matching between the tongue of the nectar bat *Anoura fistulata* and the flower of *Centropogon nigricans* [54]. However, the matching of traits is not the only pattern coevolution can induce. It can also induce a mismatch between species traits.

Indeed, traits can coevolve but don't necessarily match, which can be caused by many factors. It can for example occur if selective pressure is asymmetric, and thus the species under the stronger selective pressure can evolve “quicker” than the other. Another cause can be environmental constraints, where one species is more limited in its evolution than its partner. The last reason can be that trait mismatch can favour one of the partners. For example, the plant's main interest is to force the pollinator animal to go deep inside the flower, and thus evolution will not favour a matching flower length, but on the contrary a flower longer than the animal's body (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Summary of the two patterns of coevolution. In this example, either both partners evolve to match their traits, or the pollinator evolves to match the plant’s trait while the plant evolves to keep its trait value higher than the pollinator’s trait value.

Mutualism and biodiversity

As explained in the introduction of this section, mutualism can influence biodiversity, and coevolution is one of the mechanisms involved that can increase species richness. Indeed, coevolution can sometimes lead to cospeciation, sometimes called *codiversification*, which “refers to matching between phylogenies of interacting taxa” [1]. This is for example the case between *Crematogaster* ants and different species of *Macaranga* trees [36].

Furthermore, cospeciation is not the only mechanism through which mutualism can influence biodiversity. Indeed, as explained by Chomicki et al. [17], several macroevolutionary mechanisms driven by mutualism can increase or decrease biodiversity. They can be distinguished into two categories:

- (i) Those which have a positive impact on species richness, by increasing speciation rate, like partner shift, or by decreasing extinction rate, for example by improving survival rates.
- (ii) Those which have a negative impact, by decreasing speciation rate (e.g., “stabilizing coevolution”) or by increasing extinction rate (e.g., extinction cascades).

4 Specialisation/generalisation and dependence

Concerning mutualism, specialisation and generalisation refer to the ability of species to interact with few (specialisation) or many (generalisation) partners. This phenomenon can be asymmetric,

where one species is a specialist while its partner is more generalist (see Figure 3). Many reasons can explain why one species only interacts with a few partners, the first one being that they might be only a few species to interact with in the first place. Other reasons might be species preferences, changes in partner abundance or changes in partner quality (see Foster et al. [24] for a more complete description of these reasons in the case of herbivory). Here, as I focus on evolutionary processes, I will only consider specialisation arising from evolutionary changes in partners.

Another feature of a mutualistic interaction is the (evolved) dependence of the species interacting, defined by Chomicki et al. [16] as “a reduced ability to perform in the absence of a partner”. Combining these two concepts, Chomicki et al. [16] classify species into four categories, where species are either facultative or obligate and either specialist or generalist. However, dividing interacting species as either specialist or generalist might not be reasonable. As explained in [7], the level of specialisation is often characterized by the number of partners, and interaction between two potential partners is defined in a binary way, whether this interaction exists or not, without considering for example the frequency of the interaction. Nevertheless, many researchers focus on how to correctly quantify these interactions and try to consider their different aspects. For example, in their article, Sahli et al. [63] take into account visitation diversity, importance diversity and visitation richness, and use Simpson’s diversity index to estimate pollinator generalization.

Figure 3 – Example of interaction network between pollinators and plants. We can see that we can have interaction between two specialist partners (1), two generalist partners (2) or one generalist and one specialist partner (3).

Specialisation and dependence are closely related and thus investigating how dependence and specialisation arise, as well as how they can influence each other seem necessary to fully understand how mutualism influences their evolution.

The evolution of specialisation

An interesting approach explaining generalisation in mutualism is the one developed by Batstone et al. [4], which uses niche breadth to explain why many mutualistic partners are generalists. Firstly,

having multiple partners can be beneficial, in particular through three mechanisms that select for a broad partner set [4]:

Sampling effect: Having multiple partners can provide a more diverse sample of the partner community, and thus allow them to interact with the ones that provide the best reward.

Complementarity effect: Interacting with partners which are functionally different but provide the same type of reward but in different ways can be beneficial for the focal mutualist. Moreover, having different partners fully occupying the niche created by the provided benefits can prevent the invasion of exploiters (or cheaters) or other antagonistic species.

Portfolio effect: Having multiple partners can also reduce the influence of partner fluctuations, for example, if they have asynchronous population dynamics. In the same way, multiple partners can help the focal species to overcome ecological constraints. Indeed, each partner may have the best performance for different values of temperature, humidity, light, etc., and can then allow the focal mutualist to overcome the limitations of each partner.

Secondly, another reason can be the lack of selective pressure promoting a narrower partner breadth, as interacting with a low-quality partner is not detrimental. Finally, having multiple partners can also prevent exploitative behaviours, as cheated species can opt out of exploitative relationships and favour cooperative partners.

On the contrary, some mechanisms can promote specialisation. The first example is partner manipulation, where one species can induce its partner to change its behaviour toward it. This is the case of plant secondary metabolites found in nectar, that have for purpose to repel low-quality partners or attract high-quality partners. Partner manipulation can then promote specialisation by selecting the best partners. In the case of pollination, Johnson et al. [39] explained that “plant life history, successional status, abundance and breeding systems” can influence “the evolution of floral specialization”. Specialisation can also be explained by partner fidelity, as loyal pollinators are less likely to visit other plants and thus decrease con-specific pollen loss and hetero-specific pollen transfer.

The evolution of dependence

It seems counter-intuitive that a species would evolve to rely entirely on one or many species, as it would mean placing its survival in the hands of its partners. In their article, Chomicki et al. [16] describe four ways through which mutualistic dependence can evolve:

Dependence through ecological constraints: These constraints (e.g., geographical constraints where one species is isolated) can limit their niche, and thus the pool of potential partners. This specialisation can lead to dependence.

Dependence through specific traits: Some traits can evolve to favour a narrow subset of partners. This evolved specialisation on this subset can then lead to dependence, as the focal species might only be able to interact with this subset. An example is the obligate mutualism between long corolla-tubed plants and long-tongued flies [56].

Dependence through trait loss: In some cases, a mutualistic partner substitutes a trait originally

possessed by the now-dependent species. This is the case in the farming mutualism between the ant *Philidris nagasau* and the epiphyte *Squamellaria* cultivated by this ant species. In this example, the ant species lost the ability to build their own carton nest (made of organic materials), a loss compensated by the development of a domatium by the epiphyte [15].

Dependence through partner manipulation: A species can finally force its partner to become dependent. For example, the presence of caffeine in the floral nectar of some plants increases fidelity, and it is also the case of the mutualism between *Pseudomyrmex* and *Acacia*. In this case, the EFN of the *Acacia* inhibits the invertase activity (i.e., processing sucrose into glucose and fructose) inside ant guts, which forces them to feed exclusively on this sucrose-free EFN provided by the *Acacia*.

It is interesting to note that three of these ways (ecological constraints, specific traits, and partner manipulation) are related to specialisation, which seems to highlight the fact that dependence often occurs when species interact with only a few partners.

5 The paradox of cheating

Mutualist partners could be tempted into getting benefits without giving anything in return. For example, in the case of plant-ant mutualism, ants might consume extrafloral nectar without providing any protection against herbivory. This action is often called “cheating”. However, as explained by Jones et al. [40], as well as by Bronstein [11], many words have been used to describe this phenomenon, e.g., “exploitation”, “parasitism”, “robbers” or “thieves”. And sometimes the word “cheating” does not describe the same phenomenon, depending on the situation studied. Jones et al. [40] suggest a definition of cheating based on relative fitness to unify all the already existing definitions and define more clearly what can be seen as cheating. In their definition, cheating has to

1. Increase the fitness of the cheater higher than the average level in the population.
2. Decrease the fitness of the partner below the average level in the population.

One question is how mutualism can exist if cheating is possible. If one partner can cheat, why does the other partner still participate in this relationship?

The different forms of cheating

As described by Bronstein [11], we can distinguish three different forms (or strategies) of cheating:

Cheating as a species behaviour: Cheating can occur at a species level, where all individuals exploit partner benefits without giving anything in return. This is the case of some plants that have evolved attractive flowers (either by looking like nectar-providing flowers or resembling female insects to attract males) without providing any nectar (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Picture of an *Ophrys scolopax*, which is pollinated through pseudocopulation, where the male (bee or wasp) pollinators try to copulate with it.

Cheating as a fixed individual behaviour: Cheating can also occur at an individual level, as in the case of brood parasitism, where some individuals lay more eggs than usual, thus increasing the number of seeds eaten.

Cheating as an alternative individual behaviour: The last form designates “a behaviour used by an individual that can and does also act mutualistically on occasion”. An example are secondary robbers, pollinators that can also take nectar from holes in flowers made by primary robbers, thus not pollinating.

Stabilizing mechanisms

Cheating has an impact on the fitness of the cheated partner and thus can influence its evolutionary trajectory, by forcing it to evolve to prevent cheating or decrease its impact. In section 1, I introduced some mechanisms that can help the maintenance of mutualism, and thus they can also be helpful for the cheated partner. Host sanction, where species can change the level of reward provided according to the partner’s behaviour, can prevent the spread of cheating strategies by decreasing their advantage. Tolerance, the ability of a species to limit the negative fitness impact made by another species, can on the other side help to promote cheating strategies, but its impact on the cheated partner will be reduced. Without these mechanisms, cheating could evolve and become parasitic, where the cheater stops providing any rewards and its partner continues to provide benefits and pay the costs.

However, it is difficult to determine if these mechanisms arose to prevent cheating, or if they evolved for different reasons and maybe precede the mutualistic interaction.

6 Mathematical modelling of mutualism ecology and evolution

We saw that mutualism can widely influence the evolutionary trajectories of the species involved through many diverse mechanisms. Unfortunately, evolutionary processes are often quite difficult to investigate, as they took several hundreds of thousands of years to modify species, and thus some ecological evidence has disappeared and only the final product is studied. Another way to investigate these mechanisms is by mathematical modelling and simulations.

Population dynamics of mutualism

As explained earlier in the Introduction, the first mutualistic models were derived from the Lotka–Volterra competition model, by assuming that the species have a positive effect on each other [27]. For two species $i = 1, 2$, their population densities N_i change according to the following differential equations (with respect to time t):

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dN_1}{dt} &= r_1 N_1 \left(1 - \frac{N_1}{K_1} \right) + b_{12} N_1 N_2 \\ \frac{dN_2}{dt} &= r_2 N_2 \left(1 - \frac{N_2}{K_2} \right) + b_{21} N_1 N_2,\end{aligned}$$

both species grow logistically with intrinsic rate r_i and carrying capacity K_i in the absence of mutualism, and b_{ij} is a parameter quantifying the positive of species j on i . The stable coexistence of both species is only possible in the case where $b_{12}b_{21} < 1$, which can be interpreted as weak mutualism, (see Figure 5.A). When $b_{12}b_{21} > 1$, the model predicts unbounded population growth (see Figure 5.B).

This model considers that the positive impact of one species on the other is linearly dependent on its density, and thus as long as its density increases, so does its impact. As explained by Holland [35], this problem highlighted the need to consider diminishing returns for the benefits,[34] for example by modelling mutualistic interactions with saturating functions:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = r_i N_i \left(1 - \frac{N_i}{K_i} \right) + \frac{b_{ij} N_i N_j}{h_{ij} + N_j} \text{ with } i = 1, 2 \text{ and } j \neq i, \quad (1)$$

where h_{ij} is a half-saturation constant. Models like the above prevent unbounded growth (Figure 5.C) and further modifications predict phenomena such as mutualistic Allee effects and alternative stable states ([10] see also [52] for an alternative approach). These early models brought to light the need to take care of the density-dependent aspect of mutualism.

Figure 5 – Population dynamics of mutualism. Orange and green *isoclines* indicate density combinations for which species 1 and 2, respectively, do not grow or decline. Panels A and B display, respectively, stable coexistence (arrows point to isocline intersection) and unbounded growth (no equilibrium, arrows flow away) predicted by the Lotka–Volterra model of mutualism. Panel C shows dynamics predicted by the modified Lotka–Volterra model with saturating benefits, where growth is always bounded.

Nevertheless, the way species interact is not fixed and might depend on the densities of both species, as well as on external factors (e.g., the herbivory pressure or the quantities of resources available). All these factors can influence how relevant mutualism is for a species, and thus can influence its strength. A way to investigate these changes, which can be behavioural and/or evolutionary, is by means of Evolutionary Game Theory.

Evolutionary Game Theory

Evolutionary Game Theory (EGT) is a powerful tool to investigate mechanisms driving the adaptation and evolution of living organisms to their (abiotic and biotic) environment. EGT is derived from Game Theory, an economic-oriented framework aiming to study the outcome of interactions (called games) between rational individuals (called players) that can choose between different actions (called strategies), and where these actions will influence the outcome of the interaction. EGT replaces the rationality of the players with natural selection and the payoffs correspond to Darwinian fitness. Strategies are then phenotypes, and thus natural selection favours individuals with the phenotype which brings the highest fitness. This framework was introduced by Maynard Smith et al. [48] to investigate contests between two individuals for resources, particularly to study the evolution of aggression.

Prisoner’s Dilemma (PD) is a game especially suitable to study the evolution of mutualistic interactions [20, 73]. PD considers two strategies:

- To Cooperate
- To Defect or cheat.

Assuming that cooperation involves costs (e.g., time, resources, etc.) denoted c but brings reward (e.g., food or services) denoted b (with $b > c$), and that both species have the same cost and reward, this game can be summarised by the following bimatrix:

		Player 2	
		Cooperate	Defect
Player 1	Cooperate	$b - c$	b
	Defect	b	0

Table 1 – This bimatrix summarises the different payoffs with respect to the strategies of the focal player and of its opponent.

Now we consider a population of individuals that either cooperate or defect, and randomly meet each other, but don't know which strategy their opponent will choose. Which strategy will be favoured by natural selection? Well, if everyone cooperates, the payoff of every individual is $b - c$, however, if one of these individuals starts to defect, its payoff will be $b > b - c$, and thus, as this behaviour has a higher fitness, it should spread into the population. On the opposite, if everyone defects (with fitness 0), an individual which cooperates would have for fitness $-c < 0$, and thus this behaviour cannot spread. So, Defection seems to be the more stable strategy, as it can invade a fully cooperative population, and cannot be invaded by a cooperative individual. This strategy is then called an Evolutionary Stable Strategy (ESS) which is one of the main concepts of EGT. Moreover, we can notice that even though the previous argument helps to find this “better” strategy at an individual level, if individuals cooperate, their payoff ($b - c > 0$) would be higher. This discrepancy between individual-based natural selection (which leads to a defective population) and the benefits of a fully cooperative population can be seen as an example of the “Tragedy of the Commons” [31]. Following this simple example, cooperation should then not exist, as cheaters (or exploiters) should always have a higher fitness than cooperators. Starting from the same simple example, Nowak [55], describes five mechanisms that can lead to and maintain cooperation. While the first one (kin selection) explains cooperation between related individuals, the other four can theoretically explain how cooperation is possible between non-related individuals.

This framework can also take into account population dynamics to model for example adaptive foraging preferences [60, 44], where the strength of the mutualistic interaction depends on the quality of the reward provided, but also on the quantity available. If too many individuals already interact with the best partner, it might be better to choose another one, even if the reward provided by it has a lower quality. This kind of model often highlights the frequency-dependence of mutualistic interactions.

Evolutionary ecology of mutualism

Methods from population dynamics and EGT can be combined to study the evolution of mutualism, under approaches such as Adaptive Dynamics [50, 18, 9] or Darwinian Dynamics [70]. Starting from the idea that ecology and evolution occur together, these frameworks assume that species possess metric traits (e.g., body size, weight) affecting several ecological parameters.

For example, in equation (1), we can assume that species i has one trait x_i influencing its carrying capacity and the strength of mutualism with species j whose trait is x_j :

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = r_i N_i \left(1 - \frac{N_i}{K_i(x_i)} \right) + \frac{b_{ij}(x_i, x_j) N_i N_j}{h_{ij} + N_j} \text{ with } i = 1, 2 \text{ and } j \neq i, \quad (2)$$

and that there is some trade-off between maximising the carrying capacity and maximising interaction strength (e.g., increasing x_i causes an increase in $b_{ij}(x_i, x_j)$ but also decreases $K_i(x_i)$). Trait evolution follows fitness gradients according to equations like:

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = g_i \frac{\partial W_i}{\partial x_i}, \text{ with } W_i = \frac{dN_i}{N_i dt} \quad (3)$$

where W_i is average fitness of species i individuals, and g_i controls the speed of evolution relative to ecology. The goal then is to study the eco-evolutionary equilibrium resulting from these equations. This framework even enables *evolutionary branching* [19], speciation-like phenomena where mutant phenotypes appear and invade resident phenotypes (thus requiring additional equations for new species, e.g., [51]). By simulating speciation in this manner, questions about specialisation, generalism and partner dependence can be analyzed. Adaptive and Darwinian Dynamics approaches allow investigation of feedback between ecological dynamics and natural selection.

Aim and scope of the thesis

The mechanisms and aspects introduced in this review reflect the complexity of mutualistic interactions and thus complicate its study, as these mechanisms often interact with each other. However, approaches such as those described in the last section on mathematical modelling can facilitate understanding, by formalizing concepts such as cost, benefit, traits, specialisation vs generalism, dependence and partner choice in quantitative ways. Then, analytical and simulation methods can be used to investigate these mechanisms one by one, separately or simultaneously, to get better insights on the evolutionary ecology of mutualisms.

The main aim of my thesis is to investigate how mutualism can influence the evolution of mutualistic species by using mathematical modelling, more particularly Evolutionary Game Theory. My thesis will investigate two questions developed previously: how specialisation and dependence can appear and evolve in mutualistic interaction, and which factors can influence the evolution (or coevolution) of mutualistic traits. For this purpose, I focus on plant-animal mutualism, such as pollination and ant-plant mutualism, to find which mechanisms can influence the evolutionary trajectories of these species.

The first project of my thesis is to study coevolution in a plant-pollinator community by using Darwinian Dynamics [70], more precisely the *G-function* approach [14] to investigate under which conditions speciation can happen in a community originally composed of one monomorphic plant and one monomorphic pollinator and where the plant and the animal each have a matching pollination trait

that evolves.

These traits are assumed to influence the carrying capacities of the plant species, the plant competition and the mutualistic interaction between plant and pollinator species, such that two species (plant-plant or plant-pollinator) with similar trait values will interact more strongly than those with mismatching trait values. Considering that the plant trait determines mutualistic interaction and plant competition and carrying capacity at the same time is a simplifying assumption to obtain analytical results and can be seen as unrealistic. However, there are ecological scenarios where traits associated with mutualism and plant competition are very related. For example, a plant's peak flowering day is meant to match the annual peaks of pollinator activities [57]. But matching common pollinators with other plants species can also lead to higher levels of interspecific pollen transfer (ITP), considered an important form of plant-plant antagonism [53].

The first hypothesis is that increasing plant competition should negatively impact the ability of plant species to branch, and thus would decrease the final plant diversity. Similarly, a second hypothesis is that the degree of generalism of the pollinator species should negatively impact the ability of pollinator species to branch, and thus decrease the final pollinator diversity. A third and final hypothesis is that environmental conditions, for example, the plant carrying capacity, should influence the branching events. For example, in a harsher environment (i.e., with a lower carrying capacity), branching events should be less likely to happen.

The second project of my thesis aims to investigate with mathematical modelling the relationship between plant-pollinator interactions and the spread of a pollinator parasite in plant-pollinator bipartite networks. Indeed, pollinator parasites can spread through different pollinator species through shared plants that thus act as transmission vectors [29]. The presence of a parasite in the community can influence healthy pollinator foraging strategies, as some species are known to avoid contaminated flowers or use self-medication to decrease the risks of infection. Moreover, infected pollinators can have different foraging strategies than susceptible pollinators, and can thus participate in the pathogen transmission to new species [42].

The first hypothesis is that the architecture of plant-pollinator bipartite networks, more precisely connectance, modularity and nestedness, should influence the spread of a pathogen [58]. Indeed, highly nested networks might promote the pathogen spread [69], while high modularity might help prevent its spread to non-infected pollinator species. In the case of connectance, a highly connected network might promote interspecific pathogen transmissions [23], but could also prevent a high pathogen density through dilution effect.

The second hypothesis is that plant-pollinator traits will influence pathogen transmission in the community. For pollinators, sociality is expected to promote intraspecific transmission rate, thus increasing pathogen prevalence [58]. Moreover, pollinators' ability to detect and avoid contaminated flowers should decrease the plant-pollinator transmission rate and hence should decrease the interspecific transmission rate [58, 25, 42]. For plants, flower architecture and pollen and nectar composition could prevent pollinator species from getting infected, hence preventing the spread of the pathogen through the community [49, 25].

The third project aims to use the same framework, but this time to investigate the different mutualistic networks resulting from speciation events. In particular to study their architecture and properties to compare them with real networks. [57], [53]

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References

- [1] Bruce Anderson. “Coevolution in mutualisms”. In: *Mutualism*. Oxford University Press, 2015. Chap. 7, pp. 107–130.
- [2] Bruce Anderson et al. “The geographical mosaic of coevolution in a plant-pollinator mutualism”. In: *Evolution* 62 (2008).
- [3] Clare E. Aslan et al. “Mutualism Disruption Threatens Global Plant Biodiversity: A Systematic Review”. In: *PLoS ONE* 8 (2013), e66993.
- [4] Rebecca T. Batstone et al. “Using niche breadth theory to explain generalization in mutualisms”. In: *Ecology* 99 (2018), pp. 1039–1050.
- [5] Pierre van Beneden. *Les commensaux et les parasites dans le règne animal*. Ed. by Germer Baillière. 1878.
- [6] Peter H.W. Biedermann et al. “Ecology and Evolution of Insect–Fungus Mutualisms”. In: *Annual Review of Entomology* 65 (2020), pp. 431–455.
- [7] Nico Blüthgen et al. “Measuring specialization in species interaction networks”. In: *BMC Ecology* 6 (2006), p. 9.
- [8] D. H. Boucher et al. “The ecology of mutualism.” In: *Annual review of ecology and systematics. Volume 13* (1982).
- [9] Åke Brännström et al. “The Hitchhiker’s guide to adaptive dynamics”. In: *Games* 4 (2013), pp. 304–328.
- [10] Judith L. Bronstein. *Mutualism*. 1st ed. Oxford University Press, 2015.
- [11] Judith L. Bronstein. “The exploitation of mutualisms”. In: *Ecology Letters* 4 (2001), pp. 277–287.
- [12] Judith L. Bronstein et al. “The evolution of plant-insect mutualisms”. In: *New Phytologist* 172 (2006).
- [13] Carine Brouat et al. “Plant lock and ant key: pairwise coevolution of an exclusion filter in an ant–plant mutualism”. In: *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences* 268 (2001), pp. 2131–2141.

- [14] Anuraag Bukkuri et al. “Evolutionary game theory: Darwinian dynamics and the g function approach”. In: *Games* 12 (2021).
- [15] Guillaume Chomicki et al. “Obligate plant farming by a specialized ant”. In: *Nature Plants* 2 (2016), p. 16181.
- [16] Guillaume Chomicki et al. “The Evolution of Mutualistic Dependence”. In: *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 51 (2020), pp. 409–432.
- [17] Guillaume Chomicki et al. “The Impact of Mutualisms on Species Richness”. In: *Trends in Ecology and Evolution* 34 (2019).
- [18] Fabio Dercole et al. *Analysis of evolutionary processes: The adaptive dynamics approach and its applications*. 2008.
- [19] Michael Doebeli et al. “Evolutionary Branching and Sympatric Speciation Caused by Different Types of Ecological Interactions”. In: *The American Naturalist* 156 (2000), S77–S101.
- [20] Michael Doebeli et al. “Models of cooperation based on the Prisoner’s Dilemma and the Snowdrift game”. In: *Ecology Letters* 8 (2005), pp. 748–766.
- [21] David P. Edwards et al. “The roles of sensory traps in the origin, maintenance, and breakdown of mutualism”. In: *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology* 61 (2007), pp. 1321–1327.
- [22] Charles B. Fenster et al. “Pollination Syndromes and Floral Specialization”. In: *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 35 (2004), pp. 375–403.
- [23] Laura L. Figueroa et al. “Landscape simplification shapes pathogen prevalence in plant-pollinator networks”. In: *Ecology Letters* 23 (2020), pp. 1212–1222.
- [24] K. R. Foster et al. “A general model for the evolution of mutualisms”. In: *Journal of Evolutionary Biology* 19 (2006), pp. 1283–1293.
- [25] Bertrand Fouks et al. “Pollinator parasites and the evolution of floral traits”. In: *Ecology and Evolution* 9 (2019), pp. 6722–6737.
- [26] Megan E. Frederickson. “Rethinking Mutualism Stability: Cheaters and the Evolution of Sanctions”. In: *The Quarterly Review of Biology* 88 (2013), pp. 269–295.
- [27] G. F. Gause et al. “Behavior of Mixed Populations and the Problem of Natural Selection”. In: *The American Naturalist* 69 (1935).
- [28] Dave Goulson. “Effects of Introduced Bees on Native Ecosystems”. In: *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 34 (2003), pp. 1–26.
- [29] Peter Graystock et al. “Parasites in bloom: flowers aid dispersal and transmission of pollinator parasites within and between bee species”. In: *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 282 (2015), p. 20151371.
- [30] Juanita Gutiérrez-Valencia et al. “Recurrent breakdowns of mutualisms with ants in the neotropical ant-plant genus *Cecropia* (Urticaceae)”. In: *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 111 (2017), pp. 196–205.
- [31] Garrett Hardin. “The Tragedy of the Commons”. In: *Science* 162.3859 (1968), pp. 1243–1248. (Visited on 10/03/2022).

- [32] David H. Hembry et al. “Diversification and coevolution in brood pollination mutualisms: Windows into the role of biotic interactions in generating biological diversity”. In: *American Journal of Botany* 103 (2016).
- [33] J N Holland et al. “Mutualism”. In: *Encyclopedia of Ecology*. Ed. by Sven Erik Jørgensen et al. Academic Press, 2008, pp. 2485–2491. ISBN: 978-0-08-045405-4.
- [34] J. Nathaniel Holland et al. “Population Dynamics and Mutualism: Functional Responses of Benefits and Costs”. In: *The American Naturalist* 159 (2002), pp. 231–244.
- [35] Nathaniel J. Holland. “Population Dynamics of Mutualism”. In: *Nature Education Knowledge* 3 (2012).
- [36] Takao Itino et al. “Cospeciation of ants and plants”. In: *Ecological Research* 16 (2001), pp. 787–793.
- [37] Daniel H. Janzen. “When is it Coevolution?” In: *Evolution* 34 (1980).
- [38] Steven D. Johnson et al. “Dark, bitter-tasting nectar functions as a filter of flower visitors in a bird-pollinated plant”. In: *Ecology* 87 (2006).
- [39] Steven D. Johnson et al. “Generalization versus specialization in plant pollination systems”. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 15 (2000), pp. 140–143.
- [40] Emily I. Jones et al. “Cheaters must prosper: reconciling theoretical and empirical perspectives on cheating in mutualism”. In: *Ecology Letters* 18 (2015), pp. 1270–1284.
- [41] E. Toby Kiers et al. “Mutualisms in a changing world: An evolutionary perspective”. In: *Ecology Letters* 13 (2010).
- [42] Hauke Koch et al. “The role of disease in bee foraging ecology”. In: *Current Opinion in Insect Science* 21 (2017), pp. 60–67.
- [43] Casper J. van der Kooi et al. “The origins of flowering plants and pollinators”. In: *Science* 368 (2020), pp. 1306–1308.
- [44] Vlastimil Křivan et al. “Plant coexistence mediated by adaptive foraging preferences of exploiters or mutualists”. In: *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 480 (2019), pp. 112–128.
- [45] Lori Lach. “Argentine ants displace floral arthropods in a biodiversity hotspot”. In: *Diversity and Distributions* 14 (2007), pp. 281–290.
- [46] Alfred J. Lotka. *Elements of Physical Biology*. Williams and Wilkins Company, 1925. URL: <https://archive.org/details/elementsofphysic017171mbp>.
- [47] Andrew L. Mack. “Did fleshy fruit pulp evolve as a defence against seed loss rather than as a dispersal mechanism?” In: *Journal of Biosciences* 25 (2000), pp. 93–97.
- [48] John Maynard Smith et al. “The Logic of Animal Conflict”. In: *Nature* 246 (1973), pp. 15–18.
- [49] Scott H. McArt et al. “Arranging the bouquet of disease: floral traits and the transmission of plant and animal pathogens”. In: *Ecology Letters* 17 (2014), pp. 624–636.
- [50] J. A. J. Metz. “Adaptive Dynamics”. In: *Encyclopedia of Theoretical Ecology*. California University Press, 2012, pp. 7–17.
- [51] H. O. Minoarivelo et al. “Trait-mediated interaction leads to structural emergence in mutualistic networks”. In: *Evolutionary Ecology* 30 (2016), pp. 105–121.

- [52] Christopher M Moore et al. “Population dynamics of mutualism and intraspecific density dependence: How θ -logistic density dependence affects mutualistic positive feedback”. In: *Ecological Modelling* 368 (2017), pp. 191–197.
- [53] Carolina L. Morales et al. “Interspecific Pollen Transfer: Magnitude, Prevalence and Consequences for Plant Fitness”. In: *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences* 27 (2008), pp. 221–238.
- [54] Nathan Muchhala et al. “Going to great lengths: selection for long corolla tubes in an extremely specialized bat–flower mutualism”. In: *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 276 (2009), pp. 2147–2152.
- [55] Martin A. Nowak. “Five Rules for the Evolution of Cooperation”. In: *Science* 314 (2006), pp. 1560–1563.
- [56] Babu Ram Paudel et al. “Out of Africa: evidence of the obligate mutualism between long corolla tubed plant and long-tongued fly in the Himalayas”. In: *Ecology and Evolution* 5 (2015), pp. 5240–5251.
- [57] Guadalupe Peralta et al. “Trait matching and phenological overlap increase the spatio-temporal stability and functionality of plant–pollinator interactions”. In: *Ecology Letters* 23 (2020), pp. 1107–1116.
- [58] Willem Proesmans et al. “Pathways for Novel Epidemiology: Plant–Pollinator–Pathogen Networks and Global Change”. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 36 (2021), pp. 623–636.
- [59] Lars Råberg. “How to Live with the Enemy: Understanding Tolerance to Parasites”. In: *PLoS Biology* 12 (2014), e1001989.
- [60] Tomás A. Revilla et al. “Plant competition under simultaneous adaptation by herbivores and pollinators”. In: *Ecological Modelling* 455 (2021).
- [61] Jennifer A. Rudgers et al. “A selection mosaic in the facultative mutualism between ants and wild cotton”. In: *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences* 271 (2004), pp. 2481–2488.
- [62] J Sachs et al. “Pathways to mutualism breakdown”. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 21 (2006), pp. 585–592.
- [63] Heather F. Sahli et al. “Characterizing ecological generalization in plant-pollination systems”. In: *Oecologia* 148 (2006), pp. 365–372.
- [64] Florian P. Schiestl et al. “Pollinator-mediated evolution of floral signals”. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 28 (2013), pp. 307–315.
- [65] John N. Thompson. “Coevolution and Speciation”. In: Princeton University Press, 2013, pp. 535–542.
- [66] John N. Thompson. “Specific hypotheses on the geographic mosaic of coevolution”. In: *American Naturalist* 153 (1999).
- [67] John N. Thompson. *The Geographic Mosaic of Coevolution*. University of Chicago Press, 2005. ISBN: 9780226797625.
- [68] John N. Thompson et al. “Geographic structure and dynamics of coevolutionary selection”. In: *Nature* 417 (2002).

- [69] Lauren L. Truitt et al. “Trait-Based Modeling of Multihost Pathogen Transmission: Plant-Pollinator Networks”. In: *The American Naturalist* 193 (2019), E149–E167.
- [70] Thomas L. Vincent et al. *Evolutionary game theory, natural selection, and darwinian dynamics*. Cambridge University Press, 2005.
- [71] Vito Volterra. *Leçons sur la théorie mathématique de la lutte pour la vie*. Ed. by Gauthier-Villars et Cie. 1931.
- [72] George D. Weiblen et al. “Evolutionary origins and diversification of mutualism”. In: Oxford University Press, 2015. Chap. 3, pp. 37–56.
- [73] Feng Zhang et al. “Eco-Evolutionary Feedback and the Invasion of Cooperation in Prisoner’s Dilemma Games”. In: *PLoS ONE* 6 (2011), e27523.